

Mescalero Apache

also known as “Mescalero”, “Ndé”, “Ndénde”, “Naa'dahénde”, “Shis-Inday”, “Mashgalénde”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Native American (North American) Religions, Language, Athabaskan-Eyak-Tlingit, Athabaskan-Eyak, Athabaskan

The Mescalero Apache (also often referred to as the Mescalero) are an Athabaskan-speaking Native American ethnic group that have deep geographic ties in the American Southwest (particularly southern New Mexico and west Texas) and northwestern Mexico (primarily in northern Chihuahua and northern Coahuila). The Mescalero are famous for their long history of Mescal Agave procurement and processing, hence their modern naming convention. The Mescaleros refer to themselves as the Ndé or Ndénde (“The People”), with other preferred autonyms including Mashgalénde (“The People Near the Mountains”) and Shis-Inday (“Mountain Forest People”). While the Mescalero are historically famous for their past nomadic life ways, particularly their increased geographic reach with the adoption of the horse after European colonialism, they are also renowned for a range of complex and esoteric religious rituals that are intrinsically unique to their region, such as the female coming of age Sunrise Ceremony. The Mescalero Apache share deep linguistic and cultural ties with the Chiricahua Apache and Lipan Apache, both groups being formally a part of the modern Mescalero Apache Tribe and Reservation after regional colonialism.

Date Range: 1200 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Historic Mescalero Apache Territory

Region tags: North America

The Mescalero Apache territory has been historically and archaeologically demonstrated throughout the American Southwest and northwestern Mexico, with geographic influences and interactions extending well beyond this. This territorial extent is reflected here, prior to the relocation of the Mescalero to the modern Mescalero Apache Reservation which is within historic Mescalero territory, albeit a much smaller geographic area.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

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Print sources for understanding this subject:

ID: 4651

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Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

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https://www.google.com/books/edition/The_Medicine_men_of_the_Apache/ldwKAQAAIAAJ?hl=en&gbpv=0
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Notes: Unfortunat

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

ID: 4654

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious

ID: 4660

affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society): ID: 4661
– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice: ID: 4662
– No

↳ Assigned by class: ID: 4663
– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age: ID: 4664
– Yes
Notes: There are coming of age ceremonies for female members, the "Sunrise Ceremony."

↳ Assigned by gender: ID: 4665
– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual: ID: 4666
– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor: ID: 4667
– Yes [specify]: Community adoption of an outsider.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members: ID: 4668
– No

Does the religion have official political support ID: 4676
– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

ID: 4684

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

ID: 4685

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

ID: 4686

– Yes

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

ID: 4699

– Estimated population, numeric: 5000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

ID: 4700

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 90

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

ID:

4729

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

ID: 4745

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture: ID: 4752

– No

Is iconography present: ID: 4764

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]: ID: 4765

– On persons

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography: ID: 4766

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not): ID: 4767

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic): ID: 4768

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic): ID: 4769

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic): ID: 4770

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol): ID: 4771

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife: ID: 4772

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols): ID: 4773

– Yes

Notes: Ga'an, mountain spirits, are always represented with five individuals -- the four cardinal directions and a clown spirit

↳ Humans: ID: 4774

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography: ID: 4775

– Yes

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present: ID: 4776

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts: ID: 4777

– Yes

– No

Belief in afterlife: ID: 4780

– Yes

Notes: This is a yes and no situation. Historically, the Mescalero Apache stressed the importance of the current life - that all individuals have spirits and that upon death the respective family and community must slowly encourage the spirit to go to some concept of the beyond after four days. The Mescalero Apache have a general death taboo, and there are indications of "spirit transference" - some notion of a

type of potential rebirth. Today, many Mescalero Apache practice various sects of Christianity and believe in conceptions of the afterlife espoused within that religion, however there is a great deal of religious syncretism.

Reincarnation in this world:

ID: 4787

– Yes

Notes: To a certain extent. The Mescalero Apache have a general death taboo, and there are historical indications of "spirit transference" - some notion of a type of potential rebirth. Today, many Mescalero Apache practice various sects of Christianity and believe in conceptions of the afterlife espoused within that religion, however there is a great deal of religious syncretism.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

ID: 4794

– Yes

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

ID:

– No

4808

Are grave goods present:

ID: 4814

– No

Notes: Historically during the hunter-gatherer life way of the Mescalero Apache, grave goods were exceptionally rare due to death taboos and community interest to ease the spirit of the deceased away from the world of the living. Grave goods would encourage a connection to the world of the living

Are formal burials present:

ID:

– No

4821

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

ID:

– Yes

4827

↳ A supreme high god is present:

ID: 4828

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present: ID: 4866

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Yes and no. The goal is for human spirits to leave the mundane world shortly after physical death, within four days. Lingering spirits are not welcome as there is a death taboo, and such spirits tend to "haunt" and cause problems.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present: ID: 4897

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen: ID: 4898

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt: ID: 4899

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world: ID: 4900

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world: ID: 4911

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward: ID: 4912

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish: ID: 4913

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world: ID: 4914

- Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion: ID: 4915
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion: ID: 4916
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger: ID: 4917
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature: ID: 4918
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings: ID: 4949
 - Yes
 - ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model: ID: 4950
 - Yes
 - ↳ Organized hierarchically: ID: 4951
 - Yes
 - ↳ Power of beings is domain specific: ID: 4952
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other organization for pantheon: ID: 4953
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

ID: 4954

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular: ID: 4955

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos: ID: 4956

– Yes

↳ Food: ID: 4957

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s): ID: 4958

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s): ID: 4959

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other: ID: 4960

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists: ID: 4961

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions: ID: 4962

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities: ID: 4963

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex: ID: 4964

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying: ID: 4968

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths: ID: 4969

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness: ID: 4970

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery: ID: 4971

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting: ID: 4972

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk: ID: 4973

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders: ID: 4974

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping: ID: 4975

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes: ID: 4976

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance: ID: 4977

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals: ID: 4978

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists: ID: 4979

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness: ID: 4980

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene: ID: 4981

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other: ID: 4982

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment: ID: 4983

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known: ID: 4984

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god: ID:

- No 4985
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings: ID: 4986
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle: ID: 4987
 - No
 - ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify] ID: 4988
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known: ID: 4989
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence: ID: 4990
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms: ID: 4991
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness: ID: 4992
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly: ID: 4993
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify] ID: 4994
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife: ID:

- No 4995
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime: ID: 5002
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group: ID: 5003
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck: ID: 5004
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure: ID: 5005
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle: ID: 5006
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather: ID: 5007
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys. ID: 5008
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure: ID: 5009
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure: ID: 5010
 - No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness: ID: 5011
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction: ID:
5012
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants: ID: 5013
– Yes

↳ Other [specify] ID: 5014
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards: ID: 5015
– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known: ID: 5016
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife: ID: 5024
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime: ID: 5032
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious ID: 5033
group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck: ID: 5034
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power: ID: 5035
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle: ID: 5036
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability: ID: 5037
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather: ID: 5038
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys: ID: 5039
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure: ID: 5040
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure: ID: 5041
– No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health: ID: 5042
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success: ID: 5043
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants: ID: 5044
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

ID: 5045

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

ID: 5046

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

ID: 5077

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

ID: 5078

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

ID: 5121

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

ID: 5122

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

ID: 5127

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

ID: 5128

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is certainly a requirement for many of the Mescalero Apaches rituals, such as the Sunrise Ceremony

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods): ID: 5129

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations: ID: 5130

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds: ID: 5131

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults: ID: 5132

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children: ID: 5137

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide): ID: 5142

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items: ID: 5143

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.): ID: 5148

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking: ID: 5149

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts: ID: 5150

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members: ID: 5151

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household): ID: 5152

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals: ID: 5154
I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location: ID: 5155

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours): ID: 5156

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During the Mescalero Apache's hunter gatherer life way period, gatherings of tribal members could lead to long dance performances due to the rarity of gathering within a stationary location for long periods of time

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks: ID: 5157

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks: ID: 5158

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices: ID: 5159

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants: ID: 5160

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present: ID: 5161

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification: ID: 5162

– No

↳ Circumcision: ID: 5163

– No

↳ Food taboos: ID: 5164

– Yes

Notes: Aquatic life, bears, and coyotes were considered taboo to eat

↳ Hair: ID: 5165
– Yes

↳ Dress: ID: 5166
– Yes

↳ Ornaments: ID: 5167
– Yes
Notes: Tinklers/jinglers were important bell-like objects made out of repurposed metal from European goods and used for personal clothing, decoration for horses, and used in ritual ceremonies

↳ Archaic ritual language: ID: 5168
– No

↳ Other: ID: 5169
– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology: ID: 5170
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal: ID: 5171
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread: ID: 5172
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon: ID: 5173
– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one): ID: 5174

– A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief: ID: 5175

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5176

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief: ID: 5177

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5178

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm: ID: 5179

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5180

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents: ID: 5181

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group: ID: 5184

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group: ID: 5186

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies: ID: 5187

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage: ID: 5188

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5189

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control): ID: 5190

– No

Notes: The Mescalero Apache have become sedentary in relatively recent history. Water management is certainly a practice in the modern reservation system, but it was not necessary during past life ways

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5191

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure: ID: 5192

– Yes

Notes: Horse procurement became an introduced form of "transportation infrastructure" for the nomadic life ways of the Mescalero Apache's past history, and this became a common medium of transportation after the Spanish colonial introduction of the horse to North America.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5193

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes: ID: 5194

– Yes

Notes: Collective feasting was a means of socially-imposed sustenance taxing via resource sharing

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5195

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force: ID: 5196

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5197

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges: ID: 5198

– Yes

Notes: Tribal councils

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5199

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment: ID:

– Yes

5200

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

ID:
5201

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

ID: 5202

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

ID: 5203

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

ID: 5204

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

ID:
5205

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5206

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code: ID: 5212

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5213

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military: ID: 5214

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript: ID:
– Yes 5215

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard): ID: 5216
– No

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army: ID: 5217
– Yes

Notes: Historic community obligations of members during adulthood to be willing to defend the larger group

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5218

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5219

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language: ID: 5220

– Yes

Notes: The Mescalero Apache language did not possess written script until recent history.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5222

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5223

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar: ID: 5224

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5225

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves: ID: 5226

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]: ID: 5227

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question: ID: 5228

– No

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